

Effects of surface treatments of glass fiber on the mechanical properties of composites made from epoxy resin reinforced with wooden veneer-glass hybrid

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Abstract : The purpose of the study of this paper is to investigate some of the mechanical properties and fracture mechanism of wooden veneer-glass hybrid reinforced epoxy composite after surface treatment. To change the surface properties of glass fiber and regenerate to the hydroxyl groups activation, pre-treatment of heat cleaned woven glass fiber (GF) was performed using aqueous solution of phosphoric acid at different concentrations before silane treatment. The treatment of silanization of heat cleaned and acid activated glass fibers with γ -glycidoxy propyltrimethoxy silane were performed. In this work, tensile, flexural and impact tests have been conducted to determine the performance of the acid treatment and the silane treatment in terms of the structural strength. The silane coating on the heat cleaned glass fibers increased the tensile, flexural and impact strength of the composites, but the silane coating on the acid activated glass fibers did not improve same. Treating the glass fibers with H_3PO_4 solution followed by silane coupling agent, the tensile and flexural strengths of the composite specimens decreased significantly.

Keywords : Silanization, glycidoxypropyltrimethoxysilane, glass fibers, scanning electron photomicrographs, woven glass fiber.

Introduction

The role of matrix material in a fiber reinforced plastic (FRP) composite is three-fold : to transfer stresses between the fibers, to protect the fiber surface from mechanical abrasion along with preventing fiber or fiber dislocation; and to provide protection of the reinforcing fiber from the attack of chemical environments¹. Composite^{2,3} materials are composed of two or more components that differ in physical and chemical properties to provide desirable characteristics^{4,5}. Mechanical characteristics of fiber reinforced polymer composites depend primarily on the mechanical properties of matrix and fiber materials, the surface of the fiber and the nature of the fiber-resin bonding. These last two points are related to the surface properties of the fibers⁴. It is possible to improve the adhesion between fiber and matrix⁶⁻⁹. By surface modification techniques, such as; silane treatments or plasma techniques

(plasma treatment, plasma polymerization), the compatibility between fillers (inorganic fiber) and polymer matrices can be improved. In industry, silane coupling agents by wet chemical process are applied for surface modification of glass fiber reinforcements in order to form a functional interlayer. The silane molecules having multi-functionality react at one end with glass surface and at the other end with the polymer matrix^{4,6,10-14}. The structure of a silane coupling agent is expressed by the general formula $(RO)_3-Si-R$. Where, the (RO) group represents hydrolysable groups (methoxy, ethoxy etc.) to produce a silanol group¹⁵. This bond not only improves mechanical strength but it resists the extreme environmental conditions, such as prolonged moisture exposure and thermal cycling¹⁶. On the basis of experimental results, it was also reported that the mechanical interfacial properties of the composites decreased due to excess silane layer ab-

sorbed on to the glass fiber (GF) at higher silane coupling agent concentration. Park and Jang¹⁷ investigated the effect of the surface treatment on the mechanical properties of glass fiber/vinyl ester composites. According to Gonjalez-Benito¹⁸, the acid activation on GF greatly changes the surface composition and the hydration state. Under acidic conditions, a great number of silanol groups are generated, though an extensive number of these silanols are of internal character, greater coating degrees can be achieved¹⁹. There are only few articles dealing with pretreatment of glass fiber prior to salinization²⁰⁻²². In this study, effects of different fiber surface treatments (acid activation and silane treatment) on mechanical behavior and fracture mechanism of wood-veneer-GF hybrid epoxy composites have been investigated experimentally.

To regenerate the hydroxyl groups of GF, activation and pretreatment of heat cleaned woven glass fiber have been performed using H_3PO_4 aqueous solution (v/v) at different concentrations. The treatment of salinization of heat cleaned and acid activated GF with Y-glycidoxypropyltrimetoxysilane (Y-GPS) have been performed²³. Mechanical properties of the composites have been investigated by tensile, flexural and impact tests. The tensile and flexural properties of composites have been characterized by tensile and three-point bending test, respectively. The fracture surfaces of the composites have been observed with a scanning electron microscope (SEM)²⁴.

Experimental

Materials :

The materials used in the preparation of hybrid laminates for the present study were 'E'-glass woven glass rovings (WR) of density 0.610 kg/m^3 from Vetrotex India Pvt. Ltd., India, epoxy resin (Araldite GY257) and hardener (ARADUR 140) from Huntsman Advanced Materials India Pvt. Ltd. and wooden veneers from Priyanka Plywood, Dankuni, West Bengal, India. The silane coupling agent (Y-GPS) was supplied by Dynamite Nobel, Germany under the commercial name Dynasilan GLYMO. Phosphoric acid was of analytical grade purchased from CDH without further purification. The composition for the epoxy resin curing system is specified in the product data sheet of the manufacturer as Araldite GY257 (100 pbw) and ARADUR 140 (50 pbw) and large panels were

fabricated using wooden veneers ($1.8 \times 10^{-3} \text{ m}$ thickness) by hand lay-up technique. The basis for selection of this lay-up was that wooden veneers having the lower strength, was kept in the vicinity of the neutral axis so that it was subjected to relatively low stresses during flexural testing. The central woven glass rovings layer was used for good bonding between two layers of wooden veneers. The laminates were cure in the laboratory atmosphere for 24 h and then post cure at a temperature of $100 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 4 h. The nominal thickness of the finally cured laminate was $7.8 \times 10^{-3} \pm 0.2 \text{ m}$ having a woven glass content of 20% (by weight) and wooden veneers content 40% (by weight) as determined from the weight of individual constituents.

Surface treatment of fiber :

The 'E'-glass woven rovings were used in two forms for silanization - heat cleaned and acid activated. Heat cleaning is done at $500 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for one hour to remove any organic substances; such as sizing or impurities from the surface. Acid activation is done after heat cleaning. 'E'-glass woven roving were pretreated with aqueous H_3PO_4 solution of 1% (v/v) and 2% (v/v), separately for two hours at room temperature to regenerate the hydroxyl groups. After acid activation all samples are washed with distilled water for several times. Then all the samples are dried at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for one hour. The silane treated fibers are obtained by treating the heat cleaned 'E'-glass woven roving with acid activation followed by treatment with Y-GPS. For acid activation, aqueous acid solutions are prepared by mixing acetic acid to distilled water, adjusting the pH of the solution about 5. The silane coupling agent is added to acidified water. The mixture is stirred for about 15 min before the silanes were hydrolyzed by dilute acetic acid solution. The concentration of silane aqueous solutions was 0.4% (v/v). After 20 min of the hydrolysis reaction of Y-GPS agent, the 'E'-glass woven roving were immersed into the silane aqueous solution for two hours. Then Y-GPS treated 'E'-glass woven roving were dried for one hour at $110 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ to drive out the condensation of silanol group from the surface and to remove traces of methanol from hydrolysis of the methoxysilane.

Composite fabrication :

The epoxy resin and hardener mixture were applied to the as-received and surface treated 'E'-glass woven roving as well as wooden veneers by a hand lay-up technique. Alternate layers of woven roving and wooden ve-

neers were placed successively in between two outer layers of wooden face veneers in order to get about 8×10^{-3} m thick hybrid composite. The laminates were compressed thereafter at a pressure of 3.1×10^{-3} kg m⁻² at room temperature for 24 h and post cured at 100 °C for 4 h.

Tensile strength testing :

According to ASTM standard D 3039, tensile tests on composite sheets were performed in an Instron-1185 universal testing machine. The dumbbell shape specimens with length of 0.15 m width of 0.025 m and at the middle 0.5 m have width 0.01 m were prepared using a water jet cutter as shown in Fig. 1. Tensile tests were conducted at a constant cross head of 2×10^{-3} m min⁻¹ at room temperature in air. At least 5 specimens were tested for each type of composite sheet to check for repeatability.

Fig. 1. Dumbbell shape specimens for tensile test.

Flexural test :

The flexural strength and modulus of the wooden veneer-glass fiber hybrid epoxy composites were measured using a three-point bending test according to ASTM D 790. The three point bend fixture was manufactured by Instron for use in a universal test machine running in compression mode. At least 5 samples were measured and the results were averaged. The flexural strength (σ_f) was obtained with the following equation : $\sigma_f = 3PL / 2wt^2$, where, σ_f denotes the flexural strength. P is applied load at the moment of fracture, L is the span length and w is the width of the test specimen, and t is the thickness of the test specimen.

Sample preparation :

We prepared samples of $0.305 \times 0.305 \times 10^{-3}$ m³ composite plywood with wooden face veneers, core veneers and 'E'-glass fiber reinforced plastic cloths of 0.5×10^{-3} m thickness. The construction configuration is as follows.

Impact test :

The impact strength of the wooden veneer-glass fiber hybrid epoxy composites were measured as per ASTM D256. The sample size was $0.0635 \times 0.0127 \times 0.0032$ m³

Table 1. Thickness of individual veneer and finished composite laminate

Matrix material	Quantity used (Number)	Thickness $\times 10^3$ (m)	Total thickness $\times 10^3$ (m)
Face veneer	2	0.40	0.80
Core veneer	5	1.5	7.5
Glass fiber	2	0.40	0.80
Finished thickness : $(7.8 \pm 0.2) \times 10^{-3}$ m.			

as shown in Fig. 2. In this test the specimen is positioned across the lowest point in the path of a striker mounted at the end of a pendulum. The striker is initially lifted to a certain height h_1 and then released which swings against the sample specimen and breaks it. The striker continues its swing to the other side of the specimen to a certain height h_2 . The difference between h_1 and h_2 multiplied by the weight of the striker corresponds to the amount of energy that is absorbed in fracture.

Fig. 2. Specimens for impact strength test.

SEM analysis :

Morphological study of the composite board was done by field emission scanning electron microscope (JEOL). Magnification at x35 were used to characterize all the samples and allowed to identify their microstructure. The degradation of fiber surfaces due to acid treatment as well as the condition of fiber surfaces with the improvement of tensile strength of the composites due to the silane coupling agent treatment has been investigated.

Results and discussion

Tensile test : It is first noted that the tensile strength loss of the glass fibers is caused by an ion exchange reaction^{25,26}. The glass fibers will be chemically deteriorated as a consequence of non-siliceous ion leaching by ion-exchange reactions, i.e. the non-siliceous ions in the glass are replaced by the hydrogen ions in the acid²⁶. Mechanism of the corrosion process is accepted, an ion exchange reaction, in which metal-metal ions associated elongation

at break vary considerably depending on the acid activation treatments of heat cleaned glass fibers prior to silanization. When the 'E'-glass fiber woven roving fiber are first treated with H_3PO_4 solution and then with silane coupling agent, the tensile strengths of the composites seem to decrease significantly. It is known that the degradation of fiber strength has a direct influence on the mechanical properties of glass fiber composites because the fiber strength determines the ultimate load-bearing capacity of the composites. The decreased tensile strengths due to acid pre-treatments may be attributed to the reduction of fiber strength. Table 2 demonstrates the mechanical properties of the composite laminates. As can be seen from Table 2, when the H_3PO_4 concentration for acid pre-treatment is increased from 1% to 2%, a further decrease of the tensile strength of the composite is noticed. The tensile strength of the composites are decreased by approximately 20% for 15 min H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% Y-GPS treatment and for 2% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% Y-GPS treatment in comparison with that of the as-received sample. The decrease in fiber strength is possibly owing to chemical corrosion of glass fibers exposed to phosphoric acid. 'E'-glass is comparatively sensitive to acid attack and the soluble components are leached and resulted in siliceous hydrated material²⁷. 'E'-glass fiber compositions are presented in Table 1²⁸. It is believed that the acid treatments of the glass fibers prior to silanization may be responsible for the reduction in the tensile strength of the composites. It is thought that 2% H_3PO_4 were strong and the fibers could be further damaged by occurring the interaction between the glass surface and H_3PO_4 solution, thus resulting in lower tensile strength. On the other hand Gonzalez-Benito *et al.*¹⁹ investigated the influence of different activation pre-treat-

ments of glass fibers on the structure of an aminosilane (V-aminopropyltriethoxy silane) coupling agent layer. According to their study, under acidic condition, a great number of silanol groups are generated and greater coating degrees can be achieved. They found that the degree of silanization is the greatest for the acid activated sample. However, it is important to point out that the reduction in the tensile strength of the composites due to the chemical corrosion of glass fibers exposed to phosphoric acid plays a vital role in the performance of the composite materials. Ghosh *et al.*²⁸ also investigated the influence of 10% HCl solution, under boiling condition of 'E'-glass fiber reinforced composites. They have also noticed that 'E'-glass fiber reinforced composite suffers a very sharp loss in strength.

Flexure test : The flexural strengths of wooden veneer-glass hybrid epoxy composites are presented in Table 2. From Table 2, it is found that the flexural strength of the composite is increased only with the silane treatment on the heat cleaned glass fiber. The flexural strength is 8 enhanced by approximately 6% in comparison with that of the as-received sample. This may indicate the contribution of the silane treatment in terms of enhancement of wooden veneer-glass-epoxy adhesion. The flexural strength of fiber reinforced composites depends on the adhesion between the fiber and the matrix, as well as on the strength of both constituents¹⁰. Wang *et al.*¹¹ investigated the effect of interfacial mobility on flexural strength and fracture toughness of glass/epoxy laminates. Their results showed that the presence of silane coupling agent increased the flexural strength in both dry and wet samples. In their study, it was reported that the flexural strength increased probably due to the chemical bonding which occurs between the dissimilar phases. Shih and Eibert²⁹ also pointed out that the stronger interfacial strength leads to an in-

Table 2. Mechanical properties wooden veneer-glass hybrid/epoxy composites

Composite	EGF (Wt.)	Wooden veneer (Wt.)	Tensile strength (MPa)	Tensile modulus (GPa)	Flexural strength (MPa)	Flexural modulus (GPa)	Impact strength (J m ⁻¹)
As-received	20	40	116.83	16.20	134.69	16.52	126.19
0.4% Silane treated	20	40	125.52	17.58	142.52	19.32	191.02
1% H_3PO_4 + 0.4% Silane treated	20	40	93.40	17.62	90.42	18.62	120.01
2% H_3PO_4 + 0.4% Silane treated	20	40	36.09	15.52	27.11	17.52	105.58

The data quoted are all average result taken from a minimum of 5 tests (W/V : Weight per volume), Vf (%) : Volume fraction percentage, EGF : 'E'-Glass fiber.

crease in flexural strength. On the other hand, the flexural strengths of the composites are decreased with the acid activation treatment on the woven glass fibers. The flexural strength of the composites are decreased approximately by 32% for 1% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.3% V-GPS treatment and 79% for 2% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% V-GPS treatment in comparison with that of the as-received sample. The remarkable reduction in the mechanical properties found in the composites may be mainly the result of glass fiber damage as mentioned.

Impact test :

The results Izod impact tests of the composites show the relationships between the surface treatment of glass fibers and energy absorbing properties of the composite as given in Table 2. When the woven glass fibers are first treated with the H_3PO_4 solution particularly activated with 2% H_3PO_4 solution and then with silane coupling agent, it can be seen that the impact strength values of wooden veneer glass hybrid-epoxy composite reduced as compared to that of composites containing as-received fibers. The impact strength of the composite are decreased by approximately 5% for 1% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% V-GPS treatment of the glass fibers and 16% for 2% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% V-GPS treatment of the glass fibers in comparison with that of the as-received samples (Table 1). It is also clear from the Table 1 that the impact strength of the composites is increased by 51% for silane treatment of heat cleaned glass fibers in comparison with that of the as-received sample. It is probably that the improvement of the impact strength of the composite may be due to the chemical interaction at the interfaces between the glass fiber, wooden veneer and resin matrix.

SEM analysis :

Selected micro graph of delaminated surfaces from tensile fractured surfaces of the composites are shown in Figs. 3(a), 3(b), 4(a), 4(b). It was found that the surfaces of as-received fibers were smooth and clean and the fibers were pulled out from epoxy matrix, as shown in Fig. 3(a). There is no evidence or traces of resin matrix adhering to the fiber. Indeed, the fiber surfaces are seen to be clean and free from any adhering polymer. It is clear that the interfacial adhesion between the fibers and the matrix is poor. This observation suggests an adhesion failure in the interface. Therefore, the fracture mode of the as-received fiber reinforced composite is at the interface of the fiber-matrix and the interface structure cannot transfer stress effectively. When the fiber had undergone only the silane coupling agent surface treatment, the failure surface seems to be different from the previous case. SEM photographs of fractured surfaces of the glass fiber-epoxy composite are presented in Fig. 3(b), where the adhesion quality can be distinguished. A large amount of epoxy resin adhered to the fiber surfaces and formed a thick layer clearly indicate good interfacial interaction between the fiber and the resin and the cohesive failure at the matrix occurs. The composites treated with 2% H_3PO_4 solutions degrades the fiber surfaces much more drastically than the fiber surfaces treated with 1% H_3PO_4 solution as revealed by the corresponding scanning electron micrographs presented as Fig. 4(a) and 4(b) respectively. The results of the same studies therefore support the results of the strength analysis for evolution of the comparative stabilities of composites in different chemical environments.

Fig. 3. Scanning Electron Micro Photographs (SEM) of the fractured surface of the (a) heat cleaned (as-received) glass fiber reinforced laminate sample broken in tension, (b) Silane treated on heat cleaned (as-received) glass fiber reinforced laminate samples broken in tension.

Fig. 4. Scanning Electron Micro Photographs (SEM) of the fractured surface of the (a) 1% H_3PO_4 solution + 0.4% silane treated on heat cleaned (as-received) glass fiber reinforced laminate samples broken in tension, (b) 2% H_3PO_4 solution and 0.4% silane treated on heat cleaned (as-received) glass fiber reinforced laminate samples broken in tension.

Conclusion

The effect of the surface treatment of the glass fiber on the mechanical properties of wood veneer-glass fiber hybrid/epoxy (WVGFE) composites was investigated. The tensile strength, flexural strength and impact strength of the composite decreases due to pre-treatment of woven glass fiber with H_3PO_4 , prior to silanization. In this way a decrease in the strength is expected to occur if the surface treatment is excessive, leading to severe damage of the fiber. The tensile strength of the composites are decreased by approximately 20% for 1% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.3% V-GPS treatment and 69% for 2% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% V-GPS treatment in comparison with that of the as-received sample. The flexural strength and the impact strength of the composites are decreased by approximately 79% and 12% for 2% H_3PO_4 pre-treatment + 0.4% V-GPS treatment in comparison with that of the as-received sample, respectively. The presence of V-GPS in the composite leads to increasing tensile, flexural and impact strength of the composite by approximately 7%, 6% and 51% in comparison with that of the as-received sample respectively. These results are related to the effect of increased interfacial adhesion between glass fiber and polymer matrix. Briefly, the silane coating on the heat clean glass fiber has the beneficial effect on the adhesion between the fibers and the polymer matrix and thereby increasing the strength of the composite whereas the silane coating on the acid activated glass fiber did not improved the strength of the composites due to the fiber damage caused by H_3PO_4 solution.

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